

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN LISTENING ACTIVITIES IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Annotation: This article discusses the theoretical and practical foundations of using multimedia technologies to improve listening activities in music culture lessons. The advantages of multimedia tools in the educational process, their role in developing students' musical taste in music culture, and in forming skills for analyzing musical works are analyzed.

Keywords - music culture, multimedia technologies, listening activities, music lessons, innovative education, information technologies, aesthetic education, analysis of musical works.

Introduction.

The use of modern technologies in the educational process of the 21st century is of great importance in improving students' learning activities. The development and widespread use of multimedia technologies in education has become one of the most relevant means of increasing teaching efficiency. In particular, organizing listening activities using multimedia tools in music culture lessons not only forms students' musical taste, but also encourages them to deeply analyze and correctly understand musical works.

The main goal of the subject of musical culture is to develop aesthetic taste in students, to instill in them respect and interest in the riches of national and world music. In this case, the use of multimedia technologies allows you to make lessons more interesting, demonstrative and effective. Because modern technologies facilitate listening, analysis and understanding of various aspects of musical works.

This article discusses the theoretical foundations of the use of multimedia technologies in musical culture lessons, their advantages and possibilities of application in the teaching process. At the same time, the role of the use of multimedia tools in the development of students' musical abilities and the problems of its integration into the educational process are analyzed.

This topic is aimed at studying new approaches to modern education and improving the teaching of musical culture through them, which determines the theoretical and practical significance of the topic.

In the modern education system, the use of innovative technologies plays an important role in increasing the efficiency of the educational process. In particular, the use of modern multimedia technologies in organizing listening activities in music culture lessons allows for the formation of new educational approaches. This not only serves to develop students' musical abilities, but also to increase their interest in national and world musical heritage.

The main goal of music culture lessons is to form a musical and aesthetic taste in students, to teach them to deeply understand musical works, and to cultivate a sense of respect for cultural heritage. Traditional teaching methods may not adequately meet these goals, as they often have difficulty maintaining students' interest for a long time. Therefore, multimedia technologies appear as an urgent tool to make music lessons more lively and effective.

Multimedia tools allow organizing the music education process in an interactive, interesting and demonstrative way. In the process of listening to musical works, students can learn about composers, gain a deeper understanding of the historical, cultural and technical aspects of music. Also, through multimedia technologies, students have the opportunity to see and feel the richness of national and world music.

This article analyzes the importance of multimedia technologies in music culture lessons, their role and effectiveness in developing students' musical thinking. The relevance of the topic is based on the use of multimedia tools as a new innovative method in the educational process.

Relevance of the topic

In the modern educational process, the use of information and communication and multimedia technologies plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of teaching. In all areas of education, including music culture lessons, the use of innovative approaches is considered an important tool for increasing students' interest and facilitating the process of acquiring knowledge. Today, the widespread use of modern technologies, along with traditional methods, in teaching national and world cultural heritage is one of the pressing issues.

Music culture lessons are aimed not only at forming students' musical knowledge and skills; but also at developing their aesthetic education. However, traditional teaching methods often do not have sufficient effect in capturing

students' attention or turning them into active listeners. The wide possibilities of multimedia technologies create new, interactive opportunities for students to deeply analyze musical works, understand their history and content.

In the current era of globalization, the demand for presenting national and world musical culture to students, forming their musical thinking and developing musical taste is increasing. At the same time, multimedia tools allow not only to limit music lessons to auditory activities, but also to teach them in a demonstrative way, making lessons interesting and lively.

Also, modern trends in the field of education require taking into account international experience in music culture lessons. The use of multimedia technologies creates favorable opportunities for adapting to educational approaches that are widespread worldwide and preparing students for a modern musical environment. Therefore, the use of multimedia technologies not only increases the effectiveness of lessons, but also serves to deeply form musical and aesthetic skills in them.

The relevance of the topic is explained by the fact that the widespread use of these technologies in teaching music culture is aimed at enriching national and international educational processes and educating students as aesthetically conscious and creative individuals.

The use of multimedia technologies to improve listening skills in music culture lessons is important in making the learning process interesting and effective. The following theoretical foundations and directions can be highlighted for the topic of this article:

1. The essence and advantages of multimedia technologies

The concept of multimedia technologies: improving the learning process through the use of a combination of various information media (audio, video, graphics, text).

Advantages: involving students in the lesson, increasing the ability to deeply analyze musical works, creating an interactive learning environment.

2. Types of multimedia technologies in music culture lessons

Audio tools: listening to professional recordings of works by famous composers.

Video tools: teaching the art of musical performance through videos of orchestral, ensemble, or solo performances. Presentations: presenting visual materials on the historical context of musical works, the life and work of composers. Interactive platforms: special software for music lessons (for example, interactive musical applications).

3. Theoretical foundations

Cognitive pedagogical approaches: developing students' ability to understand and process educational material through multimedia technologies. Active approach: multimedia tools help to form students as active listeners and analysts. The principle of demonstrability: the ability to visually depict abstract musical concepts through multimedia technologies.

4. New methods of organizing lessons

Development of lesson scenarios using multimedia tools. Interactive lessons: for example, music quizzes, listening to and analyzing musical works using online platforms. Differential approach: ensuring an individual approach for students of different levels.

5. Practical application experiences

Experience of using multimedia technologies in foreign and domestic education systems. Successfully used multimedia tools and results in lessons.

6. Problems and prospects

Difficulties faced by teachers in using technologies. Adapting multimedia technologies to local conditions. Development trends and new opportunities. If necessary, I can explain each section in more detail or provide additional information in accordance with the structure of the article.

CONCLUSION

The use of multimedia technologies in musical culture lessons provides an opportunity to make the educational process more effective, interactive and demonstrative. These technologies help students develop musical and aesthetic taste, deeply analyze musical works, and also help them understand the wealth of national and world music. Multimedia tools serve as an important tool for organizing lessons in a lively, interesting and engaging way.

At the same time, the effective use of multimedia technologies teaches students not only to listen to music, but also to understand and analyze it correctly. This, in turn, develops musical thinking and strengthens students' respect for musical art and culture.

The wider use of multimedia technologies in musical culture lessons allows teachers to organize the educational process in an individual approach and interactive forms. Therefore, the effective integration of these technologies into the educational process is of great importance not only in teaching musical culture, but also in improving the general education system.

In addition, it is important for teachers to develop training courses and methodological manuals on the correct and effective use of multimedia tools in

their work. In this way, music culture lessons will further develop with the help of new technologies and play a major role in shaping students' musical knowledge and abilities.

Multimedia tools allow students to listen to musical works, understand their historical and cultural context, which makes lessons interesting and demonstrative. Through an interactive approach, students actively participate in the lesson process and find the opportunity to freely express their thoughts.

At the same time, the effective use of multimedia technologies allows teachers to organize lessons in new and innovative ways, maintain students' attention and increase their interest. All these are important factors for effective teaching of music culture.

In conclusion, the introduction of multimedia technologies into music culture lessons not only improves the quality of education, but also forms musical thinking, aesthetic understanding and respect for culture in students. This, in turn, will be an important step in improving the modern education system.

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